

QUESTIONNAIRE ON "CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF CAUSE-RELATED MARKETING"

Dear Participant,

The study aims to determine the consumers' buying behavior of FMCG products in connection with cause-related marketing. The results will be analyzed and used as part of our research work. We would be grateful if you could provide the necessary information to make this research successful. The following guidelines are provided below to help you answer the questionnaire:

The questionnaire consists of two parts. Part A and Part B. In the first part please give the correct information by ticking the box.

In the second part for all the statements a scale for instance from 'SA' to 'SD' will be given. 'SA' stands for Strongly Agree, 'A' stands for Agree, 'N' stands for Neutral, 'D' stands for Disagree, and 'SD' stands for Strongly Disagree. Kindly take a look at the scale before answering the statements. For each of the following statements, please indicate your opinion by ticking the box.

The questionnaire is anonymous and all the information will be treated confidentially and used for academic purposes.

Thank you!

PART A-DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS

1. AGE OF THE RESPONDENT.

18-35

35-55

Above 55

2. GENDER OF THE RESPONDENT.

Male

Female

Others

3. EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION OF THE RESPONDENT.

Up to matriculation

Degree

PG &Above

4. MONTHLY INCOME OF THE RESPONDENT.

Up to 20000

20000-40000

Above 40000

5. PROFESSION OF THE RESPONDENT.

Self Employed

Private Sector Employee

Government Employee

Others

6. MARITAL STATUS OF THE RESPONDENT.

Single

Married

Others

7. LOCALITY OF THE RESPONDENT.

Urban

Rural

Semi-urban

8. WHICH CATEGORY OF PRODUCT DO YOU PURCHASE MOST FREQUENTLY?

Foods & Beverages

Household Care

Personal Care

Health Care

PART B-CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR

(Please tick the extent of agreement as to the following statement. SA-Strongly Agree, A-Agree, N-Neutral, D-Disagree, SD-Strongly Disagree)

STATEMENTS	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. I give more importance to the visually appealing product package.					

<p>2. I always prefer eco-friendly product packages.</p> <p>3. I can carefully analyze the packaging cost involved by observing the price of a product.</p> <p>4. I like products having reusable packaging.</p> <p>5. I won't give importance to the label on the package of the product at the time of purchase.</p> <p>6. I won't buy products having damaged packages.</p> <p>7. I believe that companies who involve in charitable activities can improve their brand image.</p> <p>8. I always identify the product brand by checking the logo.</p> <p>9. I do not believe that the color and design of products improve the brand image.</p> <p>10. I do not have the opinion that one's personality can be revealed through their buying behavior.</p> <p>11. I am interested to purchase celebrity-endorsed products to get recognition from others.</p> <p>12. I believe that celebrities, who are part of advertisements aim for personal benefit, rather than public welfare.</p> <p>13. I do not think that celebrities are using the same product that they endorse.</p>					
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